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Pension Fund Management And Socioeconomic Welfare Of Retired Civil Servants In Rivers State, 2014 - 2024

Mpakaboari, I. D., Akujuru, C. A. & *Egobueze, A.

**Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Rivers State University, Nkpolu - Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
*anthony.egobueze@ust.edu.ng**

ABSTRACT

This study examined pension fund management and socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024. Theoretically, the paper adopted the agency theory to discuss series of interconnectivity of issues responsible for the management of pension fund. Also, the paper adopted the survey research design which involves the use of both primary and secondary data. To answer the research questions, mean value derived from the 4-Likert scale was used to determine the acceptance or agreement of a statement while Chi-square was adopted to test hypotheses at 0.05% level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected when chi-square value is greater than table value. Findings revealed among others that the scheme does not guarantee availability of funds for regular payment of pension to improve the standard of living of retirees. Lack of transparency, accountability, and integrity has frosted the relationship between pension management and socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State. The paper concluded that rigid bureaucratic processes, and political influence are major determinants that do not engender effectiveness of pension fund policies on socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State. Consequently, the paper recommended that the Rivers State government should ensure that funds are released on monthly basis to enable the pension board expedite the payment of monthly pensions as at when due.

Keywords: pension fund management, retired civil servants

INTRODUCTION

The primary challenge facing many industries, including Rivers State Civil Service, is finding effective ways to improve the socioeconomic well-being of both active and retired staff. Pension administration is a critical issue demanding urgent attention, as it directly affects retirees' quality of life. Currently, pension management in Rivers State is neither efficient nor effective, with many retirees experiencing delays, denials, or irregular payments of gratuity and pensions (Ajieh, 2014). Such deficiencies generate frustration and hardship among retirees, undermining their trust in the system.

To some civil servants, the mention of retirement invokes fear and resentment among workers, not because of retirement itself, but due to the hardships faced afterward. This fear has pushed many civil servants to falsify service records, distort their files, or alter sworn affidavits to extend their employment.

Others resort to corrupt practices such as accepting bribes, embezzling funds, or engaging in dual employment to supplement their income, all driven by anxiety about their post-retirement livelihood. Many employees avoid contemplating retirement altogether because of the negative emotions associated with this life phase (Fapohunda, 2013).

Furthermore, inconsistent government policies and poor implementation exacerbate negative perceptions of retirement in Rivers State. Davies and Lloyd (2021) note that pensioners have suffered significant hardship due to non-payment of pensions and gratuities in recent years. The rollout of pension policies has often been marred by delays, causing distress among retirees. The transition from active work to retirement is often characterized by feelings of agitation, anxiety, disappointment, anger, and injustice, which can lead to stress and health issues (Balogun, 2016). Despite these concerns, there is a lack of comprehensive retirement planning or programs to prepare workers for these psychological and financial challenges.

A key factor influencing retirees' welfare is the regular payment of pensions, which helps meet basic needs like food, clothing, housing, and healthcare, fostering dignity and self-esteem (Momoh, 2018). However, accessing pension benefits remains arduous, often involving lengthy verification processes that can result in physical stress or collapse among retirees. Pension management suffers from inadequate funding, stemming from poor budget allocation and delayed releases, which hinder timely benefit disbursement. Weak administrative practices, characterized by inefficiency and lack of transparency, further complicate pension administration. Employers frequently manipulate contributions, defaulting on payments and undermining the system's integrity .

Compounding these issues is the absence of reliable records and data on pensioners, with claims requiring up to fourteen documents for processing. Inexperienced staff and inadequate training also hinder effective pension administration. The pension system in Rivers State and Nigeria at large is fragmented and lacks a cohesive policy framework (Ngo, Egobueze, Nwaoburu, 2024). This fragmentation hampers effective management, as many personnel lack the necessary ethical standards and expertise to administer pensions properly.

This study investigates the relationship between pension fund management and the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State from 2014 to 2024. The primary objective is to assess how pension management practices influence retirees' well-being. The hypothesis tested states that there is no significant relationship between pension fund management and the socioeconomic welfare of retirees. Addressing these challenges requires systemic reforms, improved administrative capacity, transparency, and consistent policy enforcement, which can significantly enhance the quality of life for retirees and restore trust in the pension system.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

The theoretical framework guiding this study is agency theory, a concept rooted in the works of prominent scholars such as Adolf Augustus Berle and Gardiner Coit Means (1932), Stephen Ross, and Barry Mitnick. While the origins date back to the early 20th century, agency theory draws from a broad spectrum of influences, including property rights, organizational economics, contract law, and political philosophy, with foundational ideas from Locke and Hobbes. The development of agency theory as a formal discipline was significantly shaped during the 1970s by scholars like Armen Alchian, Harold Demsetz, Michael C. Jensen, William Meckling, and S. A. Ross.

Ross is credited with pioneering the economic perspective on agency, focusing on issues related to compensation and incentives. Mitnick, on the other hand, contributed the institutional dimension, emphasizing how institutions evolve around agency relationships to manage their inherent imperfections. Berle and Means (1932) initially explored agency concepts through the lens of corporate governance, analyzing conflicts of interest between managers and owners, which remain central to understanding agency problems. Jensen and Meckling (1976) further refined these ideas, framing corporations as "nexus

of contracts” where resource holders—shareholders, creditors, and managers—interact within a web of contractual relationships designed to align interests and reduce agency costs.

Agency theory fundamentally addresses two key issues: first, the divergence of interests between principals (those who delegate authority) and agents (those who act on behalf of principals), and second, the asymmetry of information and risk tolerances that can lead to conflicts. In organizational contexts, principals delegate decision-making authority to agents, trusting them to act in their best interests. However, because agents possess more information and may pursue personal goals, conflicts—known as agency conflicts—arise. These conflicts can manifest in behaviors such as misreporting, shirking, or pursuing personal gain at the expense of the principal’s objectives.

The theory posits that such conflicts generate agency costs—expenses incurred to monitor, incentivize, and align the interests of agents with those of principals. For example, implementing performance-based contracts, monitoring mechanisms, and incentive alignment tools are strategies to reduce agency costs and promote goal congruence. When agents behave in accordance with principals’ interests, the overall efficiency of the relationship improves, reducing risks and increasing trust.

Agency relationships are not limited to corporate governance; they also extend to public administration, political science, and social sciences. Historically, the agent-principal language predates formal agency theory, with early applications in political philosophy—Pitkin (1967) and Tussman (1960), for example, used similar concepts to describe representations and delegation. Swanson (1971) discussed collective society through this lens, emphasizing the importance of accountability and oversight.

In political science, Moe (1984) was among the first to explicitly introduce agency theory, applying it to understand delegation and oversight in government. Similarly, in sociology, agency concepts were incorporated by scholars like Shapiro (1987), who examined delegation and trust in social institutions. Eisenhardt (1989) extended agency theory into administrative studies, emphasizing the importance of contractual mechanisms and organizational structure.

Within the context of pension administration, agency theory provides a useful lens to analyze the relationship between government as the principal and pension fund administrators, custodians, and retirees as agents. Governments delegate responsibilities for pension management to administrators, who are expected to act in the best interests of retirees—ensuring prompt payments, transparency, and investment of pension funds. However, this relationship is often fraught with challenges, such as non-compliance with regulatory guidelines, misappropriation of funds, and delays in benefit disbursement.

Agency theory explains these issues by highlighting the potential for agents to pursue personal interests over those of the principals. For example, pension fund administrators may prioritize short-term gains or personal enrichment, neglecting their fiduciary duties to retirees. Such behavior results in agency costs—costs associated with monitoring, enforcing compliance, and implementing corrective measures. The theory underscores that the effectiveness of pension schemes depends on mechanisms that align agents’ incentives with the welfare of retirees, such as performance-based remuneration, strict regulatory oversight, and transparent reporting.

Furthermore, the theory emphasizes that the success of pension management relies on adherence to established policies and regulations, which serve as contractual safeguards to mitigate agency problems. When these mechanisms are weak or violated—as often occurs due to bureaucratic corruption or inadequate oversight—the trust of retirees erodes, and the socioeconomic welfare of pensioners declines. The failure to enforce accountability leads to delayed payments, reduced investment returns, and diminished confidence in the pension system.

In Nigeria, and specifically Rivers State, these issues are pronounced. Despite the existence of regulatory bodies such as the National Pension Commission, implementation gaps persist, resulting in irregular pension payments and misappropriation of funds. The theory suggests that strengthening oversight, improving transparency, and creating effective incentive structures are essential to mitigating agency

conflicts and ensuring that pension funds serve their intended purpose: safeguarding the socioeconomic well-being of retirees.

In conclusion, agency theory offers a comprehensive framework to analyze the complex relationships and inherent conflicts within pension management systems. It highlights the importance of designing institutions and contractual arrangements that minimize agency costs, promote transparency, and align the interests of agents with those of principals. Applying this theory to the Nigerian pension system underscores the need for robust regulatory mechanisms, accountability, and effective governance to improve the socioeconomic conditions of retirees and restore public confidence in pension institutions (Negbe & Egobueze, 2021; MoI, 2015).

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a survey research design, combining primary and secondary data through triangulation to enhance reliability and validity. The population included approximately 11,000 individuals, 10,950 retirees and 50 staff members of the Rivers State Pension Board—covering 2014 to 2024, excluding deceased retirees.

Using Taro Yamane’s formula with a 5% margin of error, a sample size of 386 respondents was determined. Purposive sampling was used to select participants based on specific criteria such as cadre level and experience, ensuring representation across board members, senior retirees, and junior retirees. Questionnaires were distributed to 178 junior pensioners, 83 staff, and 125 senior pensioners.

Data collection involved structured questionnaires, interviews, and secondary sources like scholarly articles and official reports. Primary data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive statistics such as percentages and cross-tabulations. Hypotheses testing utilized the chi-square. The chi-square formula calculated the significance of observed differences, ensuring the validity of the study’s inferences.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first section of this work dealt with socio-demographic analysis of administered and returned questionnaires while the second section analysed the responses on fundamental issues raised by the study using mean value followed by test of hypotheses and discussion of findings.

Presentation of Data

Table 1: Socio-demographic Analysis of Response Rate

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Number of questionnaires administered	386	100
Number of questionnaires not returned	36	9
Number of questionnaires retrieved	350	91
Number of questionnaires valid for the study	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2025

The table above revealed that out of the 386 questionnaires that were administered to respondents, 36 respondents making 9% of the questionnaires were not returned, 350 respondents representing 91% were successfully completed, retrieved and valid for proper analysis. The response rate is 91% and this is a mark of excellence for the study.

Table 2: Socio-demographic Analysis of Returned/Valid Questionnaires

Administration of Questionnaires	Frequency of Questionnaire Distributed	Frequency of Returned Questionnaire	Percentage (%) of Returned Questionnaire
Junior Cadre Pensioners	178	150	84
Staff of the Board	83	80	96
Senior Cadre Pensioners	125	120	96
Total	386	350	91

Source: Field Work, 2025

Data in table 2 above revealed that out of the 386 questionnaires, 150 questionnaires were returned out of 178 that were administered to respondents. Also, 80 questionnaires were returned out of 83 that were administered while 120 returned out of 125 questionnaires that were administered to respondents making 84%, 96% and 96% respectively. The response rate of total questionnaires returned is 91% which is a mark of excellence for the study.

Table 3: Socio-demographic Analysis of Gender

Gender of Respondents	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	200	57
Female	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2025

Table 3 above showed that 200 respondents representing 57% are male while 150 respondents representing 43% are female. This indicates that the majority of the respondents are male. Irrespective of their genders, their responses do not in any way interfere with the outcomes of the study as they were not biased in their views.

Table 4: Socio-demographic Analysis of Academic Background

Educational Qualifications	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
HND/BSc/PGD	200	57
MSc/MPA/MBA/PhD	150	43
Total	350	100

Source: Field Work, 2025

The table above depicted the educational qualifications of respondents and thus revealed that 200 respondents making 57% possess the Higher National Diploma (HND)/Bachelor of Science (BSc) and Postgraduate Diploma (PGD) while 150 respondents representing 43% are holders of Master of Business Administration (MBA)/Master of Public Administration (MPA)/Master of Science (M.Sc) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D). This suggests that the respondents have good knowledge of pension fund management and its effect on the socioeconomic welfare of retirees.

Data Analysis

Research Question: *How has pension fund management impacted on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants?*

Computation of response rate of how pension fund management impacted on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants.

Table 5: Shows Item 1 of Research Question: Retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	70	50	60	180	3.31	Accepted
Agreed (3)	60	20	40	120		
Disagreed (2)	15	5	10	30		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	5	5	10	20		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Item 1 of table 5 showed the views of respondents on how has pension fund management impacted on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants. In their views on whether retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly, the table shows that 180 respondents of the 350 respondents strongly agreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly with 120 respondents agreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly. However, 30 respondents

disagreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly with 20 respondents strongly disagreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly. With a mean score of 3.31, the respondents agreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly.

Table 6: Shows Item 2 of Research Question: The scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	60	20	30	110	3.09	Accepted
Agreed (3)	70	50	60	180		
Disagreed (2)	15	5	20	40		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	5	5	10	20		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The table also revealed that 110 respondents of the 350 strongly agreed that the scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension with 180 respondents agreed that the scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension. Also, 40 respondents disagreed that the scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension with 20 respondents strongly disagreed with the claim that the scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension. Based on the mean value of 3.09, the study agreed that the scheme guarantees availability of funds for regular payment of pension.

Table 7: Shows Item 3 of Research Question: Pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	5	0	0	5	1.44	Rejected
Agreed (3)	5	0	0	5		
Disagreed (2)	80	20	30	130		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	60	60	90	210		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

On whether pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees, 5 respondents strongly agreed, with 5 respondents agreed that pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees. While 130 respondents disagreed that pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees with 210 respondents strongly disagreed that pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees. With a mean score of 1.44, the study disagreed that pension administration improves the standard of living of retirees.

Table 8: Shows Item 4 of Research Question: The scheme encourages savings of retirees.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	0	0	10	10	1.5	Rejected
Agreed (3)	0	5	0	5		
Disagreed (2)	70	25	40	135		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	80	50	70	200		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

On whether the scheme encourages savings of retirees, the table above shows that 10 respondents strongly agreed with 5 agreed that the scheme encourages savings of retirees. Meanwhile, 135 respondents

disagreed that the scheme encourages savings of retirees with 200 respondents strongly disagreed that the scheme encourages savings of retirees. By a mean score of 1.5, the study rejected that the scheme encourages savings of retirees.

Table 9: Shows Item 5 of Research Question: The pension scheme is sufficient to address the challenges of retirees.

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response	Mean Value	Remark
Strongly Agreed (4)	0	0	5	5	1.6	Rejected
Agreed (3)	0	5	10	15		
Disagreed (2)	95	45	35	175		
Strongly Disagreed (1)	55	30	70	155		
Total	150	80	120	350		

Source: Survey Data, 2025

The question of whether the the pension scheme is sufficient to address the challenges of retirees, the table above also displays 5 respondents strongly agreed with 15 respondents agreed that the pension scheme is sufficient to address the challenges of retirees. 175 respondents strongly disagreed with 155 respondents disagreed that the pension scheme is sufficient to address the challenges of retirees. With a mean value of 1.6 indicates that majority of the respondents rejected that the pension scheme is sufficient to address the challenges of retirees.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis: Pension fund management has no significant impact on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024. Item 1 of research question which states that “retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly” was employed with chi-square (X^2)

thus: $X^2 = \sum \frac{(fo - fe)^2}{fe}$

Table 10: Shows responses for calculating frequency expected (fe)

Options	Junior Cadre	Pension Board	Senior Cadre	Total Response
Strongly Agreed (SA)	70	50	60	180
Agreed (A)	60	20	40	120
Disagreed (D)	15	5	10	30
Strongly Disagreed (SD)	5	5	10	20
Total	150	80	120	350

Source: Survey Data, 2025

$$fe = \frac{\text{Column total} \times \text{Row total}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

Table 11: Computation of Chi-Square Test Statistics 1

FO	FE	FO – FE	(FO – FE) ²	(FO – FE) ² /FE
70	77	-7	49	0.6
50	51	-1	1	0
60	13	47	2209	170
60	9	51	2601	289
20	41	-21	441	10.8
40	27	13	169	6.3
15	7	8	64	9.1
5	5	0	0	0
10	62	-52	2704	43.6
5	41	-36	1296	31.6
5	10	-5	25	2.5
10	7	3	9	1.3
350	350			564.8

X² Cal = 564.8**Source: Survey Data, 2025**

Tabulated at 0.05 level of significance

Hence, df = (R – 1) (C – 1)

Where:

R – number of rows,

C = number of columns

$$= (4 - 1) (3 - 1)$$

$$= (3) (2) = 6$$

From the above analysis,

df = 6

level of significance = 0.05% while

Chi-Square (X²) = 564.8

Table Value = 12.59

Decision Rule: The null hypothesis is rejected if chi-square (X²) value is greater than the table value. Here, the chi-square value = 564.8 and the table value = 12.59. It therefore signifies that the null hypothesis which states that pension fund management has no significant impact on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 – 2024 is rejected. This, in other words, means that pension fund management has no significant impact on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 - 2024.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS**Impact of pension fund management on socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants in Rivers State, 2014 – 2024.**

Data analysis revealed in item 1 of table 5 showed the views of respondents on how has pension fund management impacted on the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants. In their views on whether retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly, the table shows that 300 respondents of the 350 respondents agreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly. With a mean score of 3.31, the respondents agreed that retirees under the pension scheme get paid monthly or quarterly. This view was supported by an interviewee who thus revealed that:

There are numerous impacts of pension fund on the socioeconomic welfare of retirees. One of which is the monthly pension. In Rivers State, payment of monthly pension though, poor but it has enhanced to

an extent the socioeconomic lives of some of us. It is worthy to note that effective pension management significantly impacts the socioeconomic welfare of retirees. Properly managed pension funds provide a crucial financial foundation for retirement, influencing everything from financial security to overall well-being. It is therefore expedient to adopt an effective pension management process in any civilised society like Rivers State (A. Adolphous, personal communication, January 16, 2025).

The findings align with the research of Nwanna and Ogbonna (2022), who examined the development of pension management in Nigeria and its influence on the national economy. Their study indicated that pension management contributed significantly to Nigeria's economic growth, as evidenced by increases in retirement savings accounts, total pension assets, and pension contributions. Similarly, Handoko (2023) analyzed how pension fund characteristics—such as asset size and asset return—affect investment portfolios. The results revealed that both the size of pension fund assets and the type of pension fund considerably influence the composition of the investment portfolio. The analysis also showed that the type of pension fund exerts a positive and significant effect, while return on assets (ROA) does not have a noticeable impact on investment returns. Furthermore, the asset size of the pension fund was found to have a strong positive influence on the investment portfolio. Multiple regression analysis confirmed that asset types, pension fund categories, and ROA collectively exerted significant effects on the investment portfolio, underscoring the importance of these factors in pension fund performance (Handoko, 2023). The submission of the respondents above was aptly captured by Oladipo, Fashagba and Akindele (n.d), when they averred that:

The huge advantages of pension are no doubt responsible for the introduction of the pension legislation in the Nigeria civil service by the former colonial masters in 1951 for her expatriates. The law was to have retrospective effect from 1946. The law established the traditional non-contributory, pay-as-you-go, unfunded pension system in Nigeria. The system was not all encompassing, as until its revision in 2004, non-government employers did not normally adopt it (p.2).

The Nigerian pension system historically did not require contributions from either employees or employers, which led to significant challenges in funding retirement benefits. This lack of contributions meant that the system was often unable to fulfill its primary objective of providing adequate and timely retirement benefits to retirees. As Abdulkadir (2006) notes, the system was not necessarily a failure in its design, but it ultimately failed to meet its goals, leaving many retirees in hardship due to insufficient funds to pay their entitlements. The situation worsened in the early 2000s, causing widespread suffering among retirees. In response, reforms were initiated, culminating in the passage of the contributory pension scheme by Nigeria's National Assembly in 2004 (Oladipo, Fashagba, & Akindele, n.d). This new law aimed to replace the traditional pension system and address the persistent crisis, ensuring a more sustainable and funded approach to pension management.

A recent study's findings support the notion that the scheme provides some assurance of fund availability for pension payments. Out of 350 respondents, 290 agreed that the scheme guarantees the regular payment of pensions, reflecting a positive outlook with a mean score of 3.09. However, assessments of the scheme's impact on retirees' quality of life revealed less optimism. Only 10 respondents believed pension administration improved retirees' standard of living, and with a mean score of 1.44, the study rejected this notion. Similarly, 15 respondents agreed that the scheme encourages savings among retirees,

but the mean score of 1.5 indicated disagreement with this view. Regarding the scheme's capacity to address retirees' challenges, 20 respondents affirmed its sufficiency, yet a mean score of 1.6 suggested the majority felt it was inadequate. These results highlight ongoing concerns about the effectiveness of pension schemes in fully supporting retirees' welfare.

Secondary data emphasizes that pension management is fundamentally linked to capital accumulation, which is vital for economic growth and development. Historically, thinkers like Karl Marx and Adam Smith (1776) underscored the importance of reinvestment of profits and investment cycles in increasing capital stock, thereby fueling economic progress. Ibrahim, Dada, Ibrahim, and Alhassan (n.d) argue that capital accumulation drives wealth creation, business expansion, and overall economic advancement. Nigeria's pension funds, viewed as a form of capital investment, rely on these principles to generate returns and secure financial stability for retirees. A solid understanding of capital accumulation is essential for policymakers aiming to reform pension systems effectively. By aligning pension strategies with investment principles—such as diversification, prudent management, and wealth creation—reforms can improve fund performance and enhance retirees' welfare (Nitzan & Bichler, 2000). Promoting sustainable capital growth through careful investment can increase the resilience of pension funds and better meet Nigeria's retirees' needs (Oluitan & Falode, 2020). Exploring this theory offers valuable insights into wealth creation, investment dynamics, and economic progress, which are crucial for designing effective pension reforms.

The views expressed by respondents and interviewees align with the findings of Adewumi (2024), who observes that Nigeria's pension management system has introduced various policies aimed at fostering social welfare and an organized society. However, the realities faced by retirees remain challenging. Many retirees struggle to live comfortably due to structural issues such as corruption, misappropriation of funds, and complex pension verification processes. These problems hinder the effective delivery of pension benefits and undermine the intended social safety net for retirees, highlighting the urgent need for reforms that address these systemic challenges and improve the overall management of pension funds in Nigeria.. In agreement with the position above, an interviewee revealed that:

Pension has impacted the socioeconomic lives of retirees in some states in Nigeria. Rivers State is one of the wealthy states in Nigeria with the availability of funds to improve the standard of living of retirees. So far so good, pension is coming but it is very very insignificant to address our socioeconomic needs. Our issue is mainly on gratuity which also bore down to issues of socioeconomic welfare. We have served the state with expectation of positive response to retribution upon retirement yet our collective welfare has been constantly jeopardised. This is absolutely bad for a state like Rivers State (N. Uche, personal communication, January 16, 2025)

Etuk (2022) emphasized that within Sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria's pension management and gratuity systems are vital components of the country's broader social security agenda. Nigeria's population largely favors the younger, more dynamic demographic, while the elderly and retirees depend heavily on social security provisions for their livelihood (Fapohunda, 2013). Globally, nations in the Global North have consistently provided social security benefits through pension schemes and gratuities for retirees and the aged, ensuring economic stability in old age (Snedeker, 2017). Conversely, countries in the Global South, including Nigeria, continue to grapple with significant concerns regarding financial security for retirees (Holzmann, 2014).

In Nigeria, life after retirement is often fraught with fear and uncertainty. Animasahun and Chapman (2017) describe retirement as one of the most feared phases for Nigerian retirees, especially those in the

public sector. Tangwe and Gutura (2013) further highlight that the expectations associated with retirement tend to generate psychological, emotional, and economic distress among retirees. Ijeoma et al. (2013) link these fears to health challenges, noting that uncertainty about future income and support can negatively impact retirees' well-being. The effectiveness of Nigeria's pension management system has deteriorated, evidenced by frequent delays in pension payments and poor policy implementation, which exacerbate retirees' hardships (Fapohunda, 2013).

To address these issues, Nigeria's current pension system has introduced reforms aimed at improving efficiency. One such measure involves establishing separate agencies to handle different aspects of pension administration: the National Pension Commission (PENCOM) regulates the system; Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) manage individual retirement accounts; and Pension Fund Custodians (PFCs) safeguard pension assets (Oladipo, Fashagba, & Akindele, n.d.). While these reforms are steps in the right direction, their success depends heavily on the sincerity and cooperation of employers, who are responsible for remitting contributions timely. The pension benefits retirees receive are composed of their accumulated contributions plus investment earnings (Ogobuchi, 2007). If employers delay or fail to remit contributions, the investment earnings that would have accumulated are lost, impacting the total pension benefits at retirement. Darfman (1998) notes that such delays can have a compounding detrimental effect on the future income of retirees, reducing the overall value of their pension.

Globally, work aims to provide financial security in old age through pensions (Weber, 2010). Nigeria's inability to effectively manage pension schemes has serious consequences beyond individual hardship; it threatens family stability and social cohesion (Holzmann et al., 2004). When pension payments are delayed or withheld, retirees, especially those with dependents, face significant stress, which can lead to psychosocial issues such as social exclusion and diminished societal roles (Modigliani & Muralidhar, 2005). The government's role in providing basic social amenities and security measures is fundamental to ensuring a dignified life for citizens, particularly the elderly (Schatz et al., 2012). Well-implemented social security policies contribute to the overall well-being and economic development of a nation—robust social security systems foster stronger institutions that support sustainable economic growth (Lloyd-Sherlock et al., 2012; Sipe et al., 2015).

However, Nigeria's government faces significant structural challenges in delivering adequate social security. Abanyam (2013) observed that the federal, state, and local governments are often overwhelmed by bureaucratic and resource constraints, hampering their ability to provide effective social security protections for the large and growing retired population. Comparing the number of pensioners to the total retired population illustrates the neglect and failure of the state to fulfill its duty to protect retirees' interests (NBS, 2022). Economic difficulties have compelled many retirees to re-enter the workforce to meet their basic needs, highlighting the systemic failures in pension disbursement and social security support (Abanyam, 2013). This situation raises serious questions about the government's responsibility to ensure the financial independence and well-being of its aging citizens.

In summary, Nigeria's pension management system continues to face crises rooted in inadequate funding, poor policy implementation, and lack of effective enforcement. The reliance on reforms such as establishing regulatory bodies and custodial agencies is a positive development but insufficient without genuine commitment from employers and government agencies. The persistent delays and insufficient disbursements undermine the social contract between the state and retirees, threatening social stability. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive policy reforms, improved governance, and strengthened institutional capacity to ensure retirees receive their rightful benefits, thereby securing their dignity and economic security in old age.

The above discussion was supported by another interviewee who revealed thus that:

I want to make it outrightly clear that pension fund management in Rivers State is poor. It does not sufficiently address the needs of retirees We have suffered the socioeconomic effect of fuel subsidy

removal, inflation, and hard living with poor monthly pension and delay gratuity. There is no gainsaying about it. The system is fraudulently managed to benefit the rich. There is discrimination both in service and in pension and payment of gratuity. This is bad. I don't know what the rationale is but whatever rationale it is to us is wickedness (T. Nkiruka, personal communication, January 16, 2025).

Unarguably, the statement of the above respondent was aptly supported by Oladipo, Fashagba and Akindele (n.d), who opined that the suffering of retirees gave birth to different pension policies at every given point in time. This was to provide for the socioeconomic welfare of retired civil servants. Another interviewee reacted that:

Pension fund management has both positive and negative impacts on the socioeconomic welfare of retirees in Rivers State. The positive impact lies on the formulation of pension policies, that seek to provide financial security, improved health and well-being, reduced poverty and inequality, and enhance other socioeconomic lives of pensioners while the negative aspect deals with issues of financial instability, increased poverty and inequality, health problems and stress, and social isolation. These issues have negatively affected the socioeconomic lives of retirees in Rivers State (M. Boma, personal communication, January 16, 2025).

However, 50 respondents expressed disagreement with the notion that retirees under the pension scheme receive their payments on a monthly or quarterly basis. Additionally, 60 respondents disagreed that the scheme effectively guarantees the availability of funds for the regular payment of pensions. A significant majority, 340 respondents, also disagreed that pension administration has improved the standard of living for retirees. Similarly, 335 respondents rejected the idea that the scheme encourages savings among retirees, and 330 respondents believed that the pension scheme is insufficient to address retirees' challenges. These findings suggest that, despite the government's intentions to enhance retirees' living standards and overall welfare through pension schemes, many retirees continue to face socioeconomic hardships. The study indicates that pension fund management in Rivers State has not sufficiently addressed the socio-economic needs of retirees.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study, which focused on pension fund management and the socioeconomic wellbeing of retired civil servants in Rivers State from 2014 to 2024, reveals that, despite well-designed pension programs, the socioeconomic conditions of many retirees remain precarious. The analysis highlights that pension management practices have yet to produce meaningful improvements in retirees' lives. Several systemic issues hinder effective pension delivery, including excessive bureaucratic procedures, lack of transparency and accountability, reckless management practices, outdated financial systems, network failures, and poor coordination among relevant agencies. These challenges prevent retirees from accessing their benefits efficiently and erode public trust in the pension system.

A robust pension management system should eliminate unnecessary political and administrative interference, ensuring transparency and accountability in fund administration. It should also promote savings and capital investment, fostering economic growth and increasing retirees' financial security. Additionally, improving communication channels and fostering stakeholder engagement can boost public confidence and ensure that pension benefits genuinely enhance retirees' quality of life.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that the Rivers State government prioritize timely disbursement of pension funds, ideally on a monthly basis, to enable the pension board to process

payments promptly. The value of monthly pensions must be sufficient to meet retirees' basic needs, stimulate savings and investment, and uplift their standard of living. Pension schemes should be designed not only to meet legal obligations but also to genuinely improve retirees' socioeconomic conditions. Enhancing awareness about pension benefits and improving administrative efficiency are crucial steps toward ensuring that retirees enjoy a dignified and secure retirement.

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